

Picture fuzzy ideals of semirings

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Abstract: The aim of this paper is to introduce and study picture fuzzy ideals of a semiring in the sense of Cuong. Special attention is given to neutral membership function. Some operations on picture fuzzy ideals are defined and used them to derive some characterizations. We also obtain some characterizations of regular semiring.

Key words: Bi-ideal, Composition, Homomorphism, Ideal, Product, Picture fuzzy, Regular.

1. Introduction

Most of the problems in our practical world have various uncertainties. We cannot successfully use the crisp methods because of various uncertainties typical for these issues. To solve this, Zadeh [16] in 1965, introduced the concept of fuzzy sets, where each element has a degree of membership and has been extensively applied to many scientific fields. As a generalization of fuzzy sets, Atanassov [2] in 1986, introduced the intuitionistic fuzzy set where, besides the degree of membership of each element there was considered a degree of non-membership with (membership value + non-membership value) ≤ 1 .

After that several well-known theories, for instances, rough sets, vague sets, interval-valued sets, neutrosophic sets etc. were established to deal with various uncertainties. In 2014, Cuong [3] introduced the concept of picture fuzzy set, including the grade of neutral membership with the notion of intuitionistic fuzzy set. After that, various types of research works were done by several researchers under picture fuzzy environment. In recent days, study of algebraic structure (specially ideal theory) using picture fuzzy set is growing rapidly, for instance, see [1, 4–6, 8, 11, 12, 14, 15]. Stimulated by this, in the paper I have tried to study the ideals of semirings using the idea of picture fuzzy set, since it has several applications in automata theory, parallel computation system, combinatorics, mathematical modelling, graph theory etc. [7, 10] and derived some of its characterizations.

2. Preliminaries

We recall the following results for subsequent use.

Definition 2.1. A semiring is a nonempty set S on which operations addition and multiplication have been defined such that the following conditions are satisfied:

- (i) $(S, +)$ is a commutative monoid with identity 0 .
- (ii) (S, \cdot) is a monoid with identity 1_S .
- (iii) Multiplication distributes over addition from either side.

- (iv) $0s = 0 = s0$ for all $s \in S$.
- (v) $1_S \neq 0$.

Definition 2.2. A left ideal I of semiring S is a nonempty subset of S satisfying the following conditions:

- (i) If $a, b \in I$ then $a + b \in I$;
- (ii) If $a \in I$ and $s \in S$ then $sa \in I$;
- (iii) $I \neq S$.

A right ideal of S is defined in an analogous manner and an ideal of S is a nonempty subset which is both a left ideal and a right ideal of S .

Definition 2.3. Let R, S be semirings and $f : R \rightarrow S$ be a function. Then f is said to be a homomorphism if for all $a, b \in R$

- (i) $f(a + b) = f(a) + f(b)$
- (ii) $f(ab) = f(a)f(b)$
- (iii) $f(0_R) = 0_S$ where 0_R and 0_S are the zeroes of R and S respectively.

Definition 2.4. A semiring S is said to be regular if for each $x \in S$, there exist $a \in S$ and such that $x = xax$.

Definition 2.5. A picture fuzzy set of a set X is defined as $\mu = \{ \langle x, \alpha(x), \beta(x), \gamma(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$, where $\alpha, \beta, \gamma : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and $0 \leq \alpha(x), \beta(x), \gamma(x) \leq 1$ with $0 \leq \alpha(x) + \beta(x) + \gamma(x) \leq 1$. We refer to $\alpha(x), \beta(x)$ and $\gamma(x)$ as the degree of positive membership, neutral membership and negative membership of x , respectively. The degree of refusal membership of x in X is then defined as $1 - (\alpha(x) + \beta(x) + \gamma(x))$.

For more results on semirings and picture fuzzy sets we refer to [7, 10] and [3] respectively.

3. Main Results

Throughout this section unless otherwise mentioned S denotes a semiring.

Definition 3.1. Let $\mu = (\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ be a non empty picture fuzzy subset of a semiring S (i.e. anyone of $\alpha(x), \beta(x)$ or $\gamma(x)$ not equal to zero for some $x \in S$). Then μ is called a picture fuzzy left ideal of S if

- (i) $\alpha(x + y) \geq \min\{\alpha(x), \alpha(y)\}$, $\alpha(xy) \geq \alpha(y)$
- (ii) $\beta(x + y) \geq \frac{\beta(x) + \beta(y)}{2}$, $\beta(xy) \geq \beta(y)$
- (iii) $\gamma(x + y) \leq \max\{\gamma(x), \gamma(y)\}$, $\gamma(xy) \leq \gamma(y)$.

for all $x, y \in S$.

Similarly we can define picture fuzzy right ideal of S .

Example 3.1. Let S be the set of all positive integers. Then $(S, +, \cdot)$ forms a semiring with usual addition and multiplication of integers. Define a picture fuzzy set μ of S as follows

$$\mu(x) = \begin{cases} (1, 0, 0) & \text{if } x = 0 \\ (0.6, 0.1, 0.2) & \text{if } x \text{ is even} \\ (0.5, .02, 0.1) & \text{if } x \text{ is odd} \end{cases}$$

Then the picture fuzzy set μ of S is a picture fuzzy ideal of S .

Theorem 3.1. A picture fuzzy set $\mu = (\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ of S is a picture fuzzy left ideal of S if and only if any level subsets $\mu_t = (\alpha_t, \beta_t, \gamma_t)$ where $\alpha_t := \{x \in S : \alpha(x) \geq t, t \in [0, 1]\}$, $\beta_t := \{x \in S : \beta(x) \geq t, t \in [0, 1]\}$ and $\gamma_t := \{x \in S : \gamma(x) \leq t, t \in [0, 1]\}$ are left ideals of S .

Proof. Assume that the picture fuzzy set μ of S is a picture fuzzy left ideal of S . Then anyone of α , β or γ is not equal to zero for some $x \in S$ i.e., in other words anyone of α_t , β_t or γ_t is not equal to zero for all $t \in [0, 1]$. So it is sufficient to consider that all of them are not equal to zero.

Suppose $x, y \in \mu_t = (\alpha_t, \beta_t, \gamma_t)$ and $s \in S$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}\alpha(x+y) &\geq \min\{\alpha(x), \alpha(y)\} \geq \min\{t, t\} = t \\ \beta(x+y) &\geq \frac{\beta(x)+\beta(y)}{2} \geq \frac{t+t}{2} = t \\ \gamma(x+y) &\leq \max\{\gamma(x), \gamma(y)\} \leq \max\{t, t\} = t\end{aligned}$$

which implies $x+y \in \alpha_t, \beta_t, \gamma_t$ i.e., $x+y \in \mu_t$. Also

$$\begin{aligned}\alpha(sx) &\geq \alpha(x) \geq t \\ \beta(sx) &\geq \beta(x) \geq t \\ \gamma(sx) &\leq \gamma(x) \leq t\end{aligned}$$

Hence $sx \in \mu_t$.

Therefore μ_t is a left ideal of S .

Conversely, suppose $\mu_t (\neq \phi)$ is a left ideal of S . If possible μ is not a picture fuzzy left ideal. Then for $x, y \in S$ anyone of the following inequality is true.

$$\begin{aligned}\alpha(x+y) &< \min\{\alpha(x), \alpha(y)\} \\ \beta(x+y) &< \frac{\beta(x)+\beta(y)}{2} \\ \gamma(x+y) &> \max\{\gamma(x), \gamma(y)\}\end{aligned}$$

For the first inequality, choose $t_1 = \frac{1}{2}[\alpha(x+y) + \min\{\alpha(x), \alpha(y)\}]$. Then $\alpha(x+y) < t_1 < \min\{\alpha(x), \alpha(y)\}$ which implies $x, y \in \alpha_{t_1}$ but $x+y \notin \alpha_{t_1}$ - a contradiction.

For the second inequality, choose $t_2 = \frac{1}{2}[\beta(x+y) + \min\{\beta(x), \beta(y)\}]$. Then $\beta(x+y) < t_2 < \frac{\beta(x)+\beta(y)}{2}$ which implies $x, y \in \beta_{t_2}$ but $x+y \notin \beta_{t_2}$ - a contradiction.

For the third inequality, choose $t_3 = \frac{1}{2}[\gamma(x+y) + \max\{\gamma(x), \gamma(y)\}]$. Then $\gamma(x+y) > t_3 > \max\{\gamma(x), \gamma(y)\}$ which implies $x, y \in \gamma_{t_3}$ but $x+y \notin \gamma_{t_3}$ - a contradiction.

So, in any case we have a contradiction to the fact that μ_t is a left ideal of S .

Hence the result follows. □

Definition 3.2. Let μ and ν be two picture fuzzy subsets of S . The intersection of $\mu = (\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ and $\nu = (\zeta, \eta, \theta)$ is defined by $\mu \cap \nu = (\alpha \cap \zeta, \beta \cap \eta, \gamma \cap \theta)$ and

$$\begin{aligned}(\alpha \cap \zeta)(x) &= \min\{\alpha(x), \zeta(x)\} \\ (\beta \cap \eta)(x) &= \min\{\beta(x), \eta(x)\} \\ (\gamma \cap \theta)(x) &= \max\{\gamma(x), \theta(x)\}\end{aligned}$$

for all $x \in S$.

Proposition 3.1. *Intersection of a nonempty collection of picture fuzzy left ideals is a picture fuzzy left ideal of S .*

Proof. Let $\{\mu_i = (\alpha_i, \beta_i, \gamma_i) : i \in I\}$ be a non-empty family of picture fuzzy left ideals of S and $x, y \in S$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} (\bigcap_{i \in I} \alpha_i)(x + y) &= \inf_{i \in I} \alpha_i(x + y) \geq \inf_{i \in I} \{\min\{\alpha_i(x), \alpha_i(y)\}\} \\ &= \min\{\inf_{i \in I} \alpha_i(x), \inf_{i \in I} \alpha_i(y)\} \\ &= \min\{(\bigcap_{i \in I} \alpha_i)(x), (\bigcap_{i \in I} \alpha_i)(y)\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} (\bigcap_{i \in I} \beta_i)(x + y) &= \inf_{i \in I} \beta_i(x + y) \geq \inf_{i \in I} \frac{\beta_i(x) + \beta_i(y)}{2} \\ &= \frac{\inf_{i \in I} \beta_i(x) + \inf_{i \in I} \beta_i(y)}{2} \\ &= \frac{(\bigcap_{i \in I} \beta_i)(x) + (\bigcap_{i \in I} \beta_i)(y)}{2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} (\bigcap_{i \in I} \gamma_i)(x + y) &= \sup_{i \in I} \gamma_i(x + y) \leq \sup_{i \in I} \{\max\{\gamma_i(x), \gamma_i(y)\}\} \\ &= \max\{\sup_{i \in I} \gamma_i(x), \sup_{i \in I} \gamma_i(y)\} \\ &= \max\{(\bigcap_{i \in I} \gamma_i)(x), (\bigcap_{i \in I} \gamma_i)(y)\} \end{aligned}$$

$$(\bigcap_{i \in I} \alpha_i)(xy) = \inf_{i \in I} \alpha_i(xy) \geq \inf_{i \in I} \alpha_i(y) = (\bigcap_{i \in I} \alpha_i)(y).$$

$$(\bigcap_{i \in I} \beta_i)(xy) = \inf_{i \in I} \beta_i(xy) \geq \inf_{i \in I} \beta_i(y) = (\bigcap_{i \in I} \beta_i)(y).$$

$$(\bigcap_{i \in I} \gamma_i)(xy) = \sup_{i \in I} \gamma_i(xy) \leq \sup_{i \in I} \gamma_i(y) = (\bigcap_{i \in I} \gamma_i)(y).$$

Hence $\bigcap_{i \in I} \mu_i$ is a picture fuzzy left ideal of S . □

Proposition 3.2. *Let $f : R \rightarrow S$ be a morphism of semirings. Then*

(i) *If ϕ is a picture fuzzy left ideal of S , then $f^{-1}(\phi)$ [13] is a picture fuzzy left ideal of R .*

(ii) *If f is surjective morphism and μ is a picture fuzzy left ideal of R , then $f(\mu)$ [13] is a picture fuzzy left ideal of S .*

Proof. Let $f : R \rightarrow S$ be a morphism of semirings.

(i) Let $\phi = (\phi_T, \phi_N, \phi_F)$ be a picture fuzzy left ideal of S and $r, s \in R$.

$$\begin{aligned} f^{-1}(\phi_T)(r + s) &= \phi_T(f(r + s)) = \phi_T(f(r) + f(s)) \\ &\geq \min\{\phi_T(f(r)), \phi_T(f(s))\} = \min\{(f^{-1}(\phi_T))(r), (f^{-1}(\phi_T))(s)\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} f^{-1}(\phi_N)(r + s) &= \phi_N(f(r + s)) = \phi_N(f(r) + f(s)) \\ &\geq \frac{\phi_N(f(r)) + \phi_N(f(s))}{2} = \frac{(f^{-1}(\phi_N))(r) + (f^{-1}(\phi_N))(s)}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} f^{-1}(\phi_F)(r + s) &= \phi_F(f(r + s)) = \phi_F(f(r) + f(s)) \\ &\leq \max\{\phi_F(f(r)), \phi_F(f(s))\} = \max\{(f^{-1}(\phi_F))(r), (f^{-1}(\phi_F))(s)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Again

$$\begin{aligned} (f^{-1}(\phi_T))(rs) &= \phi_T(f(rs)) = \phi_T(f(r)f(s)) \\ &\geq \phi_T(f(s)) = (f^{-1}(\phi_T))(s) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} (f^{-1}(\phi_N))(rs) &= \phi_N(f(rs)) = \phi_N(f(r)f(s)) \\ &\geq \phi_N(f(s)) = (f^{-1}(\phi_N))(s) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}(f^{-1}(\phi_F))(rs) &= \phi_F(f(rs)) = \phi_F(f(r)f(s)) \\ &\leq \phi_F(f(s)) = (f^{-1}(\phi_F))(s)\end{aligned}$$

Thus $f^{-1}(\phi)$ is a picture fuzzy left ideal of R .

(ii) Suppose $\mu = (\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ be a picture fuzzy left ideal of R and $x', y' \in S$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}(f(\alpha))(x' + y') &= \sup_{z \in f^{-1}(x'+y')} \alpha(z) \geq \sup_{x \in f^{-1}(x'), y \in f^{-1}(y')} \alpha(x+y) \geq \sup\{\min\{\alpha(x), \alpha(y)\}\} \\ &= \min\{\sup_{x \in f^{-1}(x')} \alpha(x), \sup_{y \in f^{-1}(y')} \alpha(y)\} = \min\{(f(\alpha))(x'), (f(\alpha))(y')\}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}(f(\beta))(x' + y') &= \sup_{z \in f^{-1}(x'+y')} \beta(z) \geq \sup_{x \in f^{-1}(x'), y \in f^{-1}(y')} \beta(x+y) \geq \sup \frac{\beta(x)+\beta(y)}{2} \\ &= \frac{1}{2}[\sup_{x \in f^{-1}(x')} \beta(x) + \sup_{y \in f^{-1}(y')} \beta(y)] = \frac{1}{2}[(f(\beta))(x') + (f(\beta))(y')]\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}(f(\gamma))(x' + y') &= \inf_{z \in f^{-1}(x'+y')} \gamma(z) \leq \inf_{x \in f^{-1}(x'), y \in f^{-1}(y')} \gamma(x+y) \leq \inf\{\max\{\gamma(x), \gamma(y)\}\} \\ &= \max\{\inf_{x \in f^{-1}(x')} \gamma(x), \inf_{y \in f^{-1}(y')} \gamma(y)\} = \max\{(f(\gamma))(x'), (f(\gamma))(y')\}\end{aligned}$$

Again

$$\begin{aligned}f(\alpha)(x' y') &= \sup_{z \in f^{-1}(x' y')} \alpha(z) \geq \sup_{x \in f^{-1}(x'), y \in f^{-1}(y')} \alpha(xy) \\ &\geq \sup_{y \in f^{-1}(y')} \alpha(y) = f(\alpha)(y')\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}f(\beta)(x' y') &= \sup_{z \in f^{-1}(x' y')} \beta(z) \geq \sup_{x \in f^{-1}(x'), y \in f^{-1}(y')} \beta(xy) \\ &\geq \sup_{y \in f^{-1}(y')} \beta(y) = f(\beta)(y')\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}f(\gamma)(x' y') &= \inf_{z \in f^{-1}(x' y')} \gamma(z) \leq \inf_{x \in f^{-1}(x'), y \in f^{-1}(y')} \gamma(xy) \\ &\leq \inf_{y \in f^{-1}(y')} \gamma(y) = f(\gamma)(y')\end{aligned}$$

Thus $f(\mu)$ is a picture fuzzy left ideal of S . □

Definition 3.3. Let $\mu = (\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ and $\nu = (\zeta, \eta, \theta)$ be two picture fuzzy subsets of S . The cartesian product of μ and ν is defined by $\mu \times \nu = (\alpha \times \zeta, \beta \times \eta, \gamma \times \theta)$ and

$$(\alpha \times \zeta)(x, y) = \min\{\alpha(x), \zeta(y)\}$$

$$(\beta \times \eta)(x, y) = \frac{\beta(x) + \eta(y)}{2}$$

$$(\gamma \times \theta)(x, y) = \max\{\gamma(x), \theta(y)\}$$

for all $x, y \in S$.

Theorem 3.2. Let $\mu = (\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ and $\nu = (\zeta, \eta, \theta)$ be two picture fuzzy left ideals of S . Then $\mu \times \nu$ is a picture fuzzy left ideal of $S \times S$.

Proof. Let $(x_1, x_2), (y_1, y_2) \in S \times S$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} (\alpha \times \zeta)((x_1, x_2) + (y_1, y_2)) &= (\alpha \times \zeta)(x_1 + y_1, x_2 + y_2) \\ &= \min\{\alpha(x_1 + y_1), \zeta(x_2 + y_2)\} \\ &\geq \min\{\min\{\alpha(x_1), \alpha(y_1)\}, \min\{\zeta(x_2), \zeta(y_2)\}\} \\ &= \min\{\min\{\alpha(x_1), \zeta(x_2)\}, \min\{\alpha(y_1), \zeta(y_2)\}\} \\ &= \min\{(\alpha \times \zeta)(x_1, x_2), (\alpha \times \zeta)(y_1, y_2)\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} (\beta \times \eta)((x_1, x_2) + (y_1, y_2)) &= (\beta \times \eta)(x_1 + y_1, x_2 + y_2) \\ &= \frac{\beta(x_1+y_1)+\eta(x_2+y_2)}{2} \\ &\geq \frac{1}{2}\left\{\frac{\beta(x_1)+\beta(y_1)}{2} + \frac{\eta(x_2)+\eta(y_2)}{2}\right\} \\ &= \frac{1}{2}\left\{\frac{\beta(x_1)+\eta(x_2)}{2} + \frac{\beta(y_1)+\eta(y_2)}{2}\right\} \\ &= \frac{1}{2}\{(\beta \times \eta)(x_1, x_2) + (\beta \times \eta)(y_1, y_2)\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} (\gamma \times \theta)((x_1, x_2) + (y_1, y_2)) &= (\gamma \times \theta)(x_1 + y_1, x_2 + y_2) \\ &= \max\{\gamma(x_1 + y_1), \theta(x_2 + y_2)\} \\ &\leq \max\{\max\{\gamma(x_1), \gamma(y_1)\}, \max\{\theta(x_2), \theta(y_2)\}\} \\ &= \max\{\max\{\gamma(x_1), \theta(x_2)\}, \max\{\gamma(y_1), \theta(y_2)\}\} \\ &= \max\{(\gamma \times \theta)(x_1, x_2), (\gamma \times \theta)(y_1, y_2)\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} (\alpha \times \zeta)((x_1, x_2)(y_1, y_2)) &= (\alpha \times \zeta)(x_1y_1, x_2y_2) = \min\{\alpha(x_1y_1), \zeta(x_2y_2)\} \\ &\geq \min\{\alpha(y_1), \zeta(y_2)\} = (\alpha \times \zeta)(y_1, y_2). \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} (\beta \times \eta)((x_1, x_2)(y_1, y_2)) &= (\beta \times \eta)(x_1y_1, x_2y_2) = \frac{\beta(x_1y_1)+\eta(x_2y_2)}{2} \\ &\geq \frac{\beta(y_1)+\eta(y_2)}{2} = (\beta \times \eta)(y_1, y_2). \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} (\gamma \times \theta)((x_1, x_2)(y_1, y_2)) &= (\gamma \times \theta)(x_1y_1, x_2y_2) = \max\{\gamma(x_1y_1), \theta(x_2y_2)\} \\ &\leq \max\{\gamma(y_1), \theta(y_2)\} = (\gamma \times \theta)(y_1, y_2). \end{aligned}$$

Hence $\mu \times \nu$ is a picture fuzzy left ideal of $S \times S$. □

Theorem 3.3. Let μ be a picture fuzzy subset of S . Then μ is a picture fuzzy left ideal of S if and only if $\mu \times \mu$ is a picture fuzzy left ideal of $S \times S$.

Proof. Suppose $\mu = (\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ be a picture fuzzy subset of S . If μ is a picture fuzzy left ideal of S then by Theorem 3.2, $\mu \times \mu$ is a picture fuzzy left ideal of $S \times S$.

Conversely, suppose $\mu \times \mu$ is a picture fuzzy left ideal of $S \times S$ and $x_1, x_2, y_1, y_2 \in S$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \min\{\alpha(x_1 + y_1), \alpha(x_2 + y_2)\} &= (\alpha \times \alpha)(x_1 + y_1, x_2 + y_2) \\ &= (\alpha \times \alpha)((x_1, x_2) + (y_1, y_2)) \\ &\geq \min\{(\alpha \times \alpha)(x_1, x_2), (\alpha \times \alpha)(y_1, y_2)\} \\ &= \min\{\min\{\alpha(x_1), \alpha(x_2)\}, \min\{\alpha(y_1), \alpha(y_2)\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\beta(x_1+y_1)+\beta(x_2+y_2)}{2} &= (\beta \times \beta)(x_1 + y_1, x_2 + y_2) \\ &= (\beta \times \beta)((x_1, x_2) + (y_1, y_2)) \\ &\geq \frac{(\beta \times \beta)(x_1, x_2) + (\beta \times \beta)(y_1, y_2)}{2} \\ &= \frac{1}{2}\left[\frac{\beta(x_1)+\beta(x_2)}{2} + \frac{\beta(y_1)+\beta(y_2)}{2}\right]. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \max\{\gamma(x_1 + y_1), \gamma(x_2 + y_2)\} &= (\gamma \times \gamma)(x_1 + y_1, x_2 + y_2) \\
 &= (\gamma \times \gamma)((x_1, x_2) + (y_1, y_2)) \\
 &\leq \max\{(\gamma \times \gamma)(x_1, x_2), (\gamma \times \gamma)(y_1, y_2)\} \\
 &= \min\{\max\{\gamma(x_1), \gamma(x_2)\}, \max\{\gamma(y_1), \gamma(y_2)\}\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Now, putting $x_1 = x, x_2 = 0, y_1 = y$ and $y_2 = 0$, in the above inequalities and noting that $\alpha(0) \geq \alpha(x)$, $\beta(0) = 0$ and $\gamma(0) \leq \gamma(x)$ for all $x \in S$ we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 \alpha(x + y) &\geq \min\{\alpha(x), \alpha(y)\} \\
 \beta(x + y) &\geq \frac{\beta(x) + \beta(y)}{2} \\
 \gamma(x + y) &\leq \max\{\gamma(x), \gamma(y)\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Next, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \min\{\alpha(x_1 y_1), \alpha(x_2 y_2)\} &= (\alpha \times \alpha)(x_1 y_1, x_2 y_2) = (\alpha \times \alpha)((x_1, x_2)(y_1, y_2)) \\
 &\geq (\alpha \times \alpha)(y_1, y_2) = \min\{\alpha(y_1), \alpha(y_2)\}. \\
 \frac{\beta(x_1 y_1) + \eta(x_2 y_2)}{2} &= (\beta \times \beta)((x_1, x_2)(y_1, y_2)) \\
 &\geq (\beta \times \beta)(y_1, y_2) \\
 &= \frac{\beta(y_1) + \beta(y_2)}{2}. \\
 \max\{\gamma(x_1 y_1), \gamma(x_2 y_2)\} &= (\gamma \times \gamma)(x_1 y_1, x_2 y_2) = (\gamma \times \gamma)((x_1, x_2)(y_1, y_2)) \\
 &\leq (\gamma \times \gamma)(y_1, y_2) = \max\{\gamma(y_1), \gamma(y_2)\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Taking $x_1 = x, y_1 = y$ and $y_2 = 0$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 \alpha(xy) &\geq \alpha(y) \\
 \beta(xy) &\geq \beta(y) \\
 \gamma(xy) &\leq \gamma(y).
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence μ is a picture fuzzy left ideal of S . □

Definition 3.4. Let $\mu = (\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ and $\nu = (\zeta, \eta, \theta)$ be two picture fuzzy sets of a semiring S . Define composition of μ and ν by $\mu \circ \nu = (\alpha \circ \zeta, \beta \circ \eta, \gamma \circ \theta)$ and

$$\begin{aligned}
 (\alpha \circ \zeta)(x) &= \sup_n \{ \min_i \{ \alpha(a_i), \zeta(b_i) \} \} \\
 &\quad x = \sum_{i=1}^n a_i b_i \\
 &= 0, \text{ if } x \text{ cannot be expressed as above} \\
 (\beta \circ \eta)(x) &= \sup_n \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\beta(a_i) + \eta(b_i)}{2n} \\
 &\quad x = \sum_{i=1}^n a_i b_i \\
 &= 0, \text{ if } x \text{ cannot be expressed as above} \\
 (\gamma \circ \theta)(x) &= \inf_n \{ \max_i \{ \gamma(a_i), \theta(b_i) \} \} \\
 &\quad x = \sum_{i=1}^n a_i b_i \\
 &= 0, \text{ if } x \text{ cannot be expressed as above}
 \end{aligned}$$

where $x, a_i, b_i \in S$ for $i = 1, \dots, n$.

Theorem 3.4. *If μ and ν be two picture fuzzy left ideals of S then $\mu \circ \nu$ is also a picture fuzzy left ideal of S .*

Proof. Suppose $\mu = (\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ and $\nu = (\zeta, \eta, \theta)$ be two picture fuzzy ideals of S and $x, y \in S$. If $x + y$ cannot

be expressed as $\sum_{i=1}^n a_i b_i$, for $a_i, b_i \in S$, then we are done. Otherwise

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (\alpha \circ \zeta)(x + y) \\
 &= \sup_{x+y = \sum_{i=1}^n a_i b_i} \{ \min_i \{ \alpha(a_i), \zeta(b_i) \} \} \\
 &\geq \sup_{x = \sum_{i=1}^n c_i d_i, y = \sum_{i=1}^n e_i f_i} \{ \min_i \{ \alpha(c_i), \zeta(d_i), \alpha(e_i), \zeta(f_i) \} \} \\
 &= \min \left\{ \sup_{x = \sum_{i=1}^n c_i d_i} \{ \min_i \{ \alpha(c_i), \zeta(d_i) \} \}, \sup_{y = \sum_{i=1}^n e_i f_i} \{ \min_i \{ \alpha(e_i), \zeta(f_i) \} \} \right\} \\
 &= \min \{ (\alpha \circ \zeta)(x), (\alpha \circ \zeta)(y) \} \\
 \\
 & (\beta \circ \eta)(x + y) = \sup_{x+y = \sum_{i=1}^n a_i b_i} \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \beta(a_i) + \eta(b_i)}{2n} \\
 &\geq \sup_{x = \sum_{i=1}^n c_i d_i, y = \sum_{i=1}^n e_i f_i} \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \beta(c_i) + \eta(d_i) + \beta(e_i) + \eta(f_i)}{4n} \\
 &\geq \frac{1}{2} \left[\sup_{x = \sum_{i=1}^n c_i d_i} \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \beta(c_i) + \eta(d_i)}{2n}, \sup_{y = \sum_{i=1}^n e_i f_i} \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \beta(e_i) + \eta(f_i)}{2n} \right] = \frac{(\beta \circ \eta)(x) + (\beta \circ \eta)(y)}{2}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (\gamma \circ \theta)(x + y) = \inf_{x+y = \sum_{i=1}^n a_i b_i} \{ \max_i \{ \gamma(a_i), \theta(b_i) \} \} \\
 &\leq \inf_{x = \sum_{i=1}^n c_i d_i, y = \sum_{i=1}^n e_i f_i} \{ \max_i \{ \gamma(c_i), \theta(d_i), \gamma(e_i), \theta(f_i) \} \} \\
 &= \max \left\{ \inf_{x = \sum_{i=1}^n c_i d_i} \{ \max_i \{ \gamma(c_i), \theta(d_i) \} \}, \inf_{y = \sum_{i=1}^n e_i f_i} \{ \max_i \{ \gamma(e_i), \theta(f_i) \} \} \right\} \\
 &= \max \{ (\gamma \circ \theta)(x), (\gamma \circ \theta)(y) \}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 (\alpha \circ \zeta)(xy) &= \sup_n \left\{ \min_i \{ \alpha(a_i), \zeta(b_i) \} \right\} \\
 &\quad xy = \sum_{i=1}^n a_i b_i \\
 &\geq \sup_n \left\{ \min_i \{ \alpha(xe_i), \zeta(f_i) \} \right\} \\
 &\quad xy = \sum_{i=1}^n xe_i f_i \\
 &\geq \sup_n \left\{ \min_i \{ \alpha(e_i), \zeta(f_i) \} \right\} = (\alpha \circ \zeta)(y) \\
 &\quad y = \sum_{i=1}^n e_i f_i
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 (\beta \circ \eta)(xy) &= \sup_n \left\{ \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \beta(a_i) + \eta(b_i)}{2n} \right\} \\
 &\quad xy = \sum_{i=1}^n a_i b_i \\
 &\geq \sup_n \left\{ \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \beta(xe_i) + \eta(f_i)}{2n} \right\} \\
 &\quad xy = \sum_{i=1}^n xe_i f_i \\
 &\geq \sup_n \left\{ \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \beta(e_i) + \eta(f_i)}{2n} \right\} = (\beta \circ \eta)(y) \\
 &\quad y = \sum_{i=1}^n e_i f_i
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 (\gamma \circ \theta)(xy) &= \inf_n \left\{ \max_i \{ \gamma(a_i), \theta(b_i) \} \right\} \\
 &\quad xy = \sum_{i=1}^n a_i b_i \\
 &\leq \inf_n \left\{ \max_i \{ \gamma(xe_i), \theta(f_i) \} \right\} \\
 &\quad xy = \sum_{i=1}^n xe_i f_i \\
 &\leq \inf_n \left\{ \max_i \{ \gamma(e_i), \theta(f_i) \} \right\} = (\gamma \circ \theta)(y) \\
 &\quad y = \sum_{i=1}^n e_i f_i
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence $\mu \circ \nu$ is a picture fuzzy left ideal of S . □

Definition 3.5. A picture fuzzy subset $\mu = (\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ of a semiring S is called picture fuzzy bi-ideal if for all $x, y, z \in S$ we have

- (i) $\alpha(x + y) \geq \min\{\alpha(x), \alpha(y)\}$, $\alpha(xy) \geq \min\{\alpha(x), \alpha(y)\}$, $\alpha(xyz) \geq \min\{\alpha(x), \alpha(z)\}$
- (ii) $\beta(x + y) \geq \frac{\beta(x) + \beta(y)}{2}$, $\beta(xy) \geq \frac{\beta(x) + \beta(y)}{2}$, $\beta(xyz) \geq \frac{\beta(x) + \beta(z)}{2}$
- (iii) $\gamma(x + y) \leq \max\{\gamma(x), \gamma(y)\}$, $\gamma(xy) \leq \max\{\gamma(x), \gamma(y)\}$, $\gamma(xyz) \leq \max\{\gamma(x), \gamma(z)\}$

Definition 3.6. A picture fuzzy subset $\mu = (\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ of a semiring S is called picture fuzzy quasi-ideal if for all $x, y, z \in S$ we have

- (i) $\alpha(x + y) \geq \min\{\alpha(x), \alpha(y)\}$
- (ii) $\beta(x + y) \geq \frac{\beta(x) + \beta(y)}{2}$
- (iii) $\gamma(x + y) \leq \max\{\gamma(x), \gamma(y)\}$
- (iv) $(\alpha \circ \chi_S) \cap (\chi_S \circ \alpha) \subseteq \alpha$
- (v) $(\beta \circ \chi_S) \cap (\chi_S \circ \beta) \subseteq \beta$
- (vi) $(\gamma \circ \chi_S) \cap (\chi_S \circ \gamma) \supseteq \alpha$

From the definition of picture fuzzy bi-ideal and picture fuzzy quasi-ideal we can immediately get the following result.

Theorem 3.5. Any picture fuzzy quasi-ideal of S is a picture fuzzy bi-ideal of S .

In [9], Kondo et al. introduced the Transfer Principle in fuzzy set theory, from which a picture fuzzy sets can be characterized by its level subsets. For any algebraic system $\mathcal{U} = (X, F)$, where F is a family of operations defined on X , the Transfer Principle can be formulated as follows:

A fuzzy subset defined on \mathcal{U} has the property \mathcal{P} if and only if all non-empty level subset μ_t have the property \mathcal{P} .

As a direct consequence of the above Result, the following results can be obtained.

Theorem 3.6. Let S be a semiring. Then

- (i) $\mu = (\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ is a picture fuzzy left (resp. right) ideal of S if and only if all level subsets $\mu_t = (\alpha_t, \beta_t, \gamma_t)$ are left (resp. right) ideals of S .
- (ii) $\mu = (\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ is a picture fuzzy bi-ideal of S if and only if all level subsets $\mu_t = (\alpha_t, \beta_t, \gamma_t)$ are bi-ideals of S .
- (iii) $\mu = (\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ is a picture fuzzy quasi-ideal of S if and only if all level subsets $\mu_t = (\alpha_t, \beta_t, \gamma_t)$ are quasi-ideals of S .

Now upto calculations, we obtain the following characterizations of regular semirings. Note that for any two picture fuzzy subsets $\mu = (\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ and $\nu = (\zeta, \eta, \theta)$ of S , $\mu \subseteq \nu$ implies $\alpha \subseteq \zeta$, $\beta \subseteq \eta$ and $\gamma \supseteq \theta$.

Theorem 3.7. A semiring S is regular if and only if for any picture fuzzy right ideal μ and any picture fuzzy left ideal ν of S we have $\mu \circ \nu = \mu \cap \nu$.

Theorem 3.8. Let S be a semiring. Then the following conditions are equivalent.

- (i) S is regular.
- (ii) $\mu \subseteq \mu \circ \chi_S \circ \mu$ for every picture fuzzy bi-ideal μ of S .
- (iii) $\mu \subseteq \mu \circ \chi_S \circ \mu$ for every picture fuzzy quasi-ideal μ of S .

Theorem 3.9. Let S is a semiring. Then the following conditions are equivalent.

- (i) S is regular.
- (ii) $\mu \cap \nu \subseteq \mu \circ \nu \circ \mu$ for every picture fuzzy bi-ideal μ and every picture fuzzy ideal ν of S .
- (iii) $\mu \cap \nu \subseteq \mu \circ \nu \circ \mu$ for every picture fuzzy quasi-ideal μ and every picture fuzzy ideal ν of S .

Conclusion: This is the introductory paper on picture fuzzy ideals of semirings in the sense of Cuong [3]. Here we define three operations intersection, cartesian product and compositions of picture fuzzy ideals and use these to find some description. I think, by parallel computations these results can also be derived for Γ -semiring.

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